

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D8.2 – Communication and Collaboration Plan and Activities I

WP8 Communication and Exploitation

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Executive summary

The Communication and Collaboration Plan and Activities-I deliverable has a key role in laying down the principles for designing the communication and dissemination strategy activities to be followed throughout the project. The dissemination and communication strategy consist of spreading awareness of the project and its results, among specialists, general public and emerging stakeholders. To achieve these results, it will target diverse groups of people – depending on the specific goals, e.g., engage partners, inform a specific category of patients – through different media, so to maximize the spreading impact; and using a variety of tools, conceived and chosen based on the specific target.

As communication and dissemination activities are running in parallel with the development of all work packages, they are in sync with the process, progress and feedback that the project receives. Therefore, the activities can and should be adapted along the way. As the initial publication package submitted – with all dissemination communication activities reported – at a very early stage of the project implementation (M2), it acts mostly as a roadmap, laying down a common understanding and an overview of the communication activities that might be needed while subject to regular monitoring and adjustment.

This document will start with the purpose of the deliverable and its correlation with the other project's deliverables and tasks, followed by the dissemination strategy and the planning of activities. We will describe iHelp dissemination channels and present promotional material and online promotion strategies.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Deliverable

The purpose of the document is to present the dissemination plans for the iHelp and the key dissemination material that consortium partners should have available, in order to have a homogeneous strategy and approach to execute dissemination activities. The dissemination plans are mainly based on the initial planning presented in the DoA. However, considering an agile planning and execution of dissemination activities, the project will continuously review the planning, aiming to have a strong impact.

A number of specific communication activities will be developed in order to implement the dissemination strategy and to pave the way for future exploitation of the project outcome, such as: (a) setting up and administrating the technical infrastructure, (b) creating appropriate communication material, (c) engaging in outreach initiatives towards the industry, the scientific community and standards organizations, and (d) developing business plans, market research and market take-up material.

The mainly objectives of this document are first of all to spread awareness of the project's outcomes among the general public and reach audience that could boost the marketing, exploitation and sustainability of the project's results later in time.

1.2 Relation with other Deliverables and Tasks

The activities of WP8 receive inputs from all tasks and deliverables of the iHelp project. In this deliverable, all project partners have contributed, and the results of other WPs are presented and communicated.

2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

2.1 Dissemination Strategy Objectives

The major focus of the iHelp dissemination and communication plan is to ensure that the project activities and outcomes are widely spread among the appropriate target communities, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods. It should be pointed out that dissemination and communication activities and channels described in the following sections are linked to the exploitation of the project results.

The dissemination strategy has the following objectives:

- To identify targeted stakeholders;
- To define the communication tools that will be used and develop the dissemination plan to increase the impact of the project;
- To create public awareness of the project and its results;
- To ensure that the knowledge and information gained will be made available to multiple targets at national, European and global level;
- To ensure that the project activities and outcomes are widely spread among the appropriate target communities, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods;
- To foster communication with other projects.

2.2 Communication Activities

2.2.1 Overview of Communication Activities

The communication activities related to the dissemination, set by the project from its proposal phase are grouped as follows:

- Create Project Identity and Branding material, as well as, create publicity materials e.g., Leaflet/brochure;
- Website design and social media accounts – Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube. These are the public communication resources for the project, where the target is more than 1000 followers overall, during the project duration;
- Project mailing lists, which will support project's internal communications and public lists for outward communications;
- Attend and/or host up to 20 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and end-users overall, during the project duration;
- Generate media coverage and releasing at least 10 project publications and more than 30 blog entries overall, during the project duration;

2.2.2 Communication Phases

The iHelp project will follow a 3-step communication approach with the following phases:

- Phase 1: Awareness raising;
- Phase 2: Dissemination;
- Phase 3: Exploitation.

In the following sections, the overall activities of each phase are described. Furthermore, the WP8/T8.1 leader will follow on monthly basis the concrete activities from all partners. For this purpose, three shared worksheets will be maintained by the project; see Table 2: Overview of activities; Events and Campaigns.

2.2.2.1 Awareness

The awareness raising phase will cover the period from M1 to M12, in which the project will prepare the branding of the project (Milestone MS1) and the high-level conceptual model and reference architecture (Milestone MS2). The communication objectives of this phase, are mainly to raise awareness of the project, enhance visibility, and build a network to be capitalised at the next phase. Serving those objectives requires solid identification and analysis of the stakeholders and target groups (as will be analysed below), development of a set of appropriate communication messages and tools, and assurance of quality outputs and results to show for.

2.2.2.2 Dissemination

Having reached milestones MS1 and MS2, the project will have results to demonstrate. The results will be delivered continuously, so the audience can be in touch with the project's progress. By the time we reach this phase, all stakeholders and target groups will have been identified and their needs analysed, many communication tools will have been developed and key activities prepared while the network will be underway and synergies will be in place. The challenge of this phase is to capitalise on the achievements of the iHelp project, securing the maintenance of stakeholders' interest and engagement, encouraging participation. At the same time, this phase benefits from the lessons learned during the previous phase. A careful evaluation of the progress during the previous phase and the challenges addressed will need to feed into the Communication Strategy to be crafted and adjusted at this stage.

2.2.2.3 Exploitation

This phase includes communication activities that will be linked with the exploitation strategy of the project and will be introduced in D8.5 (Exploitation plan I).

2.3 Target Groups

The target groups that have been identified as potential stakeholders of iHelp project are classified in five major categories, namely:

- TG1: ICT Technology and Service Providers ;
- TG2: Healthcare Service Providers ;
- TG3: Academic and Scientific Community ;
- TG4: Policy Makers and Facilitators ;
- TG5: Public at large .

3 Individual Dissemination and Communication Plans

In this section we report for each consortium member their individual plans for disseminating the project's outcomes.

3.1 University of Piraeus Research Centre (UPRC)

Since University of Piraeus Research Centre (UPRC) belong to the University of Piraeus, its major advantage is that everything developed in the context of iHelp will be disseminated, exploited, and furtherly used for research and education purposes. Hence, in this context the designed components and mechanisms under the scopes of T3.4 "Standardisation and Quality Assurance of Heterogeneous Data" will be exploited by students, researchers, and the academic faculty – when and if needed – while it will be offered as an online independent software to specific developers and stakeholders in the form of a ready to use component and as an API or serverless service. Moreover, UPRC as the Project Manager of the project will drive the communication and dissemination of the scientific and technical know-how developed in the project to relevant research activities. To this end, specific papers and publications will also be produced and will be presented and published in different scientific conferences and journals.

Finally, UPRC, as an academic organization addresses research in the domain of software engineering and distributed computing. Based on the above, UPRC dissemination strategy will be in the context of UPRC's strategic plans and more specifically the iHelp results and approaches will be proliferated among the attendants of the University activities, through postgraduate and continuing education programs.

3.2 Athens Technology Centre (ATC)

The dissemination activities to be performed by Athens Technology Center (ATC) partner, aim to raise awareness of the project's outcomes to a broad audience including researchers, medical institutes, policy makers and citizens. The channels that will be used, in a regular basis, include the ATC's official website (www.atc.gr), "Twitter" page (twitter.com/atc_gr), "LinkedIn" page (gr.linkedin.com/company/athens-technology-center) and "Facebook" page (www.facebook.com/athenstechnologycenter).

The dissemination actions include the active presence in social media not only via reposting the published material from the iHelp dissemination social media, but also by creating new content and publishing it in ATC's Website and social media platforms. Moreover, special effort will be given, to continue publishing the produced outcomes in relevant Conferences, Symposiums (such as the IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications) and scientific Journals. Finally, due to the company's intense involvement in the provision of AI mechanisms (algorithms & techniques) for the early prediction of Pancreatic Cancer risk factors, special Blog Posts will be created for the announcement of progress in the relevant field.

3.3 LeanXcale (LXS)

LeanXcale (LXS) will disseminate the project's outcomes that related to the iHelp knowledge management system to potential clients in the healthcare sector (e.g., care service providers, hospitals, public health organizations). LXS will take advantage of relevant dissemination and communication opportunities towards promoting and showcasing the use of the LeanXcale BigData database in Healthcare AI use cases. Its target objective is to create awareness in the industry about the innovations developed in the project to prepare for large scale commercialization after project end. The targeted markets are Europe, Asia and US, while the target sectors that are the ones that are data intensive and rely on isolated silo.

An indicative list of planned activities that LXS plans to organize in order to contribute towards the dissemination and communication of the project is:

- Conferences / Exhibitions / trade fair
- Webinars: bimonthly webinar on the project use cases.
- Press releases, newspaper articles and other dissemination activities.

Moreover, LXS plans to publish frequently posts on data management until the end of the project at LinkedIn network (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/leanxcale/>).

3.4 KODAR Systems (KOD)

KODAR (KOD) and its affiliate partners – Strypes and DS4 – are technical partners and technical communication channels for dissemination of information about the project, scope and involved innovations will be utilized.

KODAR and his partners will announce the project and his goals during the technical conferences and events any of them is participating and especially the AI, big data processing and enterprise products related ones.

In parallel, the news and events section of the corresponding corporate websites (<https://www.kodar.net/>, <https://digisys4.eu/>) will be updated with information about internal project milestones reached that contain task where associated partner has participated.

KODAR's social media profiles, LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/kodar/>), Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/KodarLtd/>) will be used as well to announce project goals and targets along with other company driven or supported social responsibility initiatives

The auditory of those channels is not limited to developers but also include a general public that follow the companies and their initiatives.

Last but very important and influential channel are personal social media profiles of participants in the project - most of them recognisable among the fowlers as advocates of healthy living.

3.5 Innovation Sprint (iSPRINT)

Innovation Sprint (iSPRINT) is the leader of the WP8, Dissemination and Exploitation of the project and therefore manages all communication activities of the iHelp project.

As a project partner, Innovation Sprint will actively raise awareness for the iHelp project to stakeholders around Good Clinical Practice (GCP) and participate in conferences and events from the pharmaceutical industry.

Innovation Sprint will also promote this European project through a range of content material it will produce through its site (www.innovationsprint.eu) and social media channels, Twitter (<https://twitter.com/innovSprint>), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovation-sprint/>), Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/innovationsprint.eu>). The target audience of all these communications is people from the pharma industry, regulators, policymakers, and researchers.

Furthermore, the iHelp solution can be presented at the annual workshop organized by Innovation Sprint in the first months of 2022 (Sprint 5th Workshop), with news considering actions taken and project's results.

Finally, Innovation Sprint has already published a Press Release with the general overview of the iHelp project. The audience for this Press Release is in media containing global pharmaceutical news and resources.

3.6 Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SpA (ENG)

Engineering Ingegneria Informatica (ENG) addresses dissemination task directly involving its Marketing and Communication group and exploiting the company channels to reach all the group with premises worldwide. Specifically, we use to exploit: our website (<https://www.eng.it/en/>) as well as LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/engineering-ingegneria-informatica-spa/>), Twitter (<https://twitter.com/EngineeringSpa>), Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/lifeatengineering/>) to advertise about our projects and achievements in agreement with a well-established company policy and strategy which periodically communicates with the R&D to showcase about its main Research & Innovation achievements. In case of relevant results or events, it is also possible to issue press releases.

As an additional mean of internal communication within the group (i.e. worldwide) and, as a consequence towards the external world via our sales managers, the possibility to organize thematic webinars on project results, to write instant papers, white papers, to give interviews or to report on specific case studies.

In terms of dissemination, this is primarily performed by visiting our customers and the institutional stakeholders (central, regional and local government) to showcase our main innovations, by participating to public events (e.g., Digital Health Summit, EHTEL Symposium) for presenting projects and our main contributions. Further, we consider participating together with other (academic) partners in writing scientific manuscripts for conferences or journals, even though it is not core to our business and strategy.

3.7 Siemens (SIE)

Siemens (SIE) is building its communication and dissemination plan based on internal policy and the current positioning related to the EU level organizations and associations. As a relevant community, Siemens is aiming to own internal R&D and also business units staff in order to meaningfully reach customers and business partners.

At the EU level, Siemens plans to use the extensive networking generated by past or current projects to link with and create cross-domain information exchange and support.

We plan to present project outcomes and generate awareness via partnerships with BDVA (Big Data Value Association, <https://www.bdva.eu/>).

Further, follow-up on preparing and providing the project's contributions to international standards consortiums is envisioned, e.g., Industrial Internet Consortium, as well as to EU clusters and associations, as appropriate, considering the outcomes of T8.2 and for collaboration and cross-referencing on trustworthiness and compliance.

Specific iHelp findings related to Siemens's involvement and project outcomes will be promoted towards Siemens Healthineers (www.siemens-healthineers.com), and social network accounts (e.g., LinkedIn, Twitter).

We envision inter-projects communications and clustering activities with other running co-funded projects, e.g. Retention (<https://www.retention-project.eu/>), HEIR (<https://heir2020.eu/>), Eur3ka

(<https://www.eur3ka.eu/>), EFPF (<https://www.efpf.org/>), STAR (<https://star-ai.eu/>) or ASCAPE (<https://ascape-project.eu/>), which share research interests and conduct research in similar topics, notably topics related to IoT devices, AI, Big Data and security considering health data for evaluating healthy risks, assure secure telemedicine or smart manufacturing. In case common data exists, it will leverage secure interconnections, or support building the AI models for disease predictions and risk identification. In the latter case, some medical traits representative for one disease might have implications for another disease. Therefore, investigating similar projects can provide increased performances and discover hidden linkages.

Early identification of prospective stakeholders and engage them in the project ecosystem for community development and prospective marketplace is also to be considered. Participation at scientific events (workshops, conferences) in order to raise awareness about iHelp and dissemination to scientific journals and conferences with contributions from partners related to the corresponding project activities, will also be performed, accordingly.

3.8 Information Catalyst for Enterprise (ICE)

Information Catalyst for Enterprise (ICE) will promote the iHelp project through various channels, including but not limited to the use of company website (<https://informationcatalyst.com/>) to broadcast project's achievements, the use of company social media channels as well as the presentations/brochures/banners at the industry events and exhibitions (e.g., Big Data London, Big Data World etc) where the company regularly participates. Moreover, ICE will prepare targeted dissemination material in the form of videos and brochures highlighting niche value proposition of the project in various technological and healthcare areas. The prepared material will be made available on the project's website and social media channels, LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/information-catalyst/>), Twitter (<https://twitter.com/InfoCatalystUK>), Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/infocatalystUK>).

3.9 Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) as an academic partner will disseminate the project results in master lectures to introduce students to data visualization techniques and the low code programming model used by the Decision Support System (DSS). UPM participates in an EIT Health master programme where iHelp results will be presented.

UPM organizes seminars on topics related to health research at least once per year where the results of iHelp will be disseminated. These seminars are attended by clinicians and hospital staff that might be interested in the iHelp results. Until now, there has been a strong collaboration with an expert oncologist working with lung cancer. The DSS is used in this project in the context of pancreatic cancer but, it is independent of the specific type of cancer and can be used by a wide spectrum of clinicians. UPM has transferred previously several research results to the industry and will look for opportunities for transferring the iHelp results (mainly the DSS) to interested parties. The DSS will be open source with an Apache license.

Some research publications on the DSS are foreseen and one is already being written.

3.10 University of Manchester (UNIMAN)

University of Manchester (UNIMAN) will be engaging with all dissemination activities of our work. Professor Kenneth Muir had already contributed to the broadcast video in the Pancreatic Cancer Day programme on

the project's YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSeeFSLYsDneHLMr6r62MOA>). In terms of academic disseminations of our work, we submitted abstracts related to two aspects of iHelp including an innovative pancreatic risk predictive model and the development of the iHelp platform as way to advertise our iHelp project as a whole. Furthermore, we will continue to disseminate our outcome to reputational journals such as Cancer Epidemiology Biomarkers & Prevention journal (<https://cebp.aacrjournals.org/>), British Journal of cancer (<https://www.nature.com/bjc/>) and Plos One (<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/>).

3.11 Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic (FPG)

Fondazione Policlinico Gemelli (FPG) aims to promote the iHelp project through both academy- and general public-oriented dissemination activities.

FPG plans to share iHelp progress and results with the general public through its official social network accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter) and website (www.gemelligenerator.it).

FPG will also be committed to sharing iHelp outcomes with researchers from the medical and hospital management field by publishing high-quality review and experimental papers in the following journals (see Table 1 below).

Table 1: Target Journals for Gemelli Hospital.

Journal	URL
The Lancet Oncology	https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanonc
Cancers	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/cancers
Frontiers in Oncology	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/oncology
Artificial Intelligence in Medicine	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/artificial-intelligence-in-medicine
World journal of gastroenterology	https://www.wjgnet.com/1007-9327/
Technology in Cancer Research and Treatment	https://journals.sagepub.com/home/tct

3.12 Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud (HDM)

The Communication and Corporate Social Responsibility Department of the Dénia Marina Salud Hospital (HDM) widely disseminates communications related to health promotion and its projects. The iHelp project and its development is communicated in different ways; internally to all professionals and through external communication to the population of Marina Alta and the general public, as well as to other health institutions and organisations.

The Hospital's Department of Communication and Corporate Social Responsibility takes great care with communications through different channels, including social networks, the Hospital's intranet and website, workshops, institutional events, patient information events, etc. All these elements are available to Marina Salud and all iHelp partners to promote the results of the project.

- **HDM Communication Channels:**
 - Marina Salud website: <https://www.marinasalud.es/>
 - Marina Salud Intranet: <https://marinanet.happydonia.com/>
- **HDM Social Networks:**

- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/HospitaldeDenia>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/marina-salud>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/c/MarinaSaludHospitaldeDenia>

- **Media:**

- Local and national newspapers
- Local radio stations
- Health newspapers

3.13 Karolinska Institutet (KI)

Karolinska Institutet (KI) aims to support and promote the iHelp project through both academy- and general public-oriented dissemination activities.

KI plans to share iHelp progress and results through its official social network accounts, LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/school/karolinska-institutet/>), Twitter (<https://twitter.com/innovSprint>) and other relevant channels.

KI will also be committed to sharing iHelp outcomes with researchers from the medical field/scientific community by being co-author/s in scientific papers/publishing.

3.14 Medical University Plovdiv (MUP)

Medical University of Plovdiv (MUP) is leading the pilot for iHelp platform evaluation and implementation into the medical specialists practice.

As a project partner and in order to organize and fulfil successfully the task related to the pilot, MUP team has started to advertise and discuss the iHelp project objective and clinical value of the IT platform that will be created and proposed to practitioners and population at risk. The main aim of these first communication activities is to inform the clinical medical specialist for the application that will facilitate the early diagnosis of already developed Pancreatic cancer in first stages, as well as to identify the patients with elevated risk for development of this malignant process.

The second group of activities that are at the starting point at this stage of the project development is to present the project and its achievements to the Bulgarian Scientific Clinical Associations on General Medicine, Internal Medicine, Gastroenterology, General and Abdominal Surgery and Clinical Oncology, which could benefit from the iHelp platform by its inclusion it into their practice. In this sense, the primary steps have been performed and the Bulgarian Medical Association Regional Head has been informed in order to start organizing the presentation to the mentioned Scientific Societies.

The communication plan of the MUP include presentations of the project activities and results on national and international scientific conferences related to the mentioned specialties.

The project results will be also presented to the Bulgarian Scientific Association for Public Health at national conferences as well to the Director of the Regional Healthcare Inspection Plovdiv for implementing the platform into the directives regarding the Good Medical Practices.

Considering communication, a plan for addressing the Medical Academia is foreseen, aiming include the platform into the undergraduate and postgraduate university programs, thus enhancing the medical community capabilities for more effective prevention and early diagnosis of Pancreatic cancer as well as a better management of the patients with already developed cancer.

3.15 Taipei Medical University Foundation (TMU)

Taipei Medical University (TMU) will promote the results of the study through publication of articles in esteemed journals, presentations / workshops / panels in conferences, introducing the study through social media before the study as well as benefits and implementation after the study, to create public awareness, on the health policy arising as a result of the iHelp project. TMU will strive (i) to formulate the important messages targeted at different stakeholders (ii) to disseminate the required solutions and outcomes of pilots to the medical communities through networking, social media, conferences and other platforms to increase project awareness; (iii) to assess the impact of dissemination (iv) to seek feedback on the expectations of the relevant stakeholders. To summarize, TMU will contribute to the growth and development of iHelp solutions in the Asia-Pacific region.

TMU has initiated disseminating the project introduction and TMU's contribution in iHelp through workshops and lectures, targeted towards scientific community in Taiwan, India and Indonesia.

4 Project Website

The iHelp website will be the main tool for disseminating and communicating the project activities. Its main purpose is to inform the different stakeholders about the project and become an important source of information for both general public and experts in the area, aiming to create awareness of project activities.

All the news regarding the iHelp project will be published on the website while the iHelp consortium will measure the analytics related to the website impact onto the general public. Moreover, the iHelp's website acts as a scientific blog area where each partner is invited to publish its own article. More specifically, during this first year of the project 13 scientific blog posts have been created from 13 different partners to enhance the communication and dissemination of the project's outcomes and the work and research that are carried out in the context of the iHelp project.

The site is hosted in the following address: www.ihelp-project.eu

The screenshot displays the iHelp project website homepage. The header includes the iHelp logo, navigation links (Home, The Project, Pilots, Partners, News, Contact), and a search icon. The main banner features an illustration of healthcare professionals and a central text box stating: "iHelp will focus on Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based on AI and HH Records design". Below this is a "Get Started" button.

The "Project's Vision" section describes the focus on early identification and mitigation of risks associated with Pancreatic Cancer, utilizing advanced AI-based learning and decision support techniques on the iHelp Consortium's data of Cancer patients. It outlines three key steps:

- Determine key risks associated with Pancreatic Cancer
- Develop predictive models for identified risks
- Develop adaptive models for targeted prevention and intervention measures

The "Pilot Studies" section lists five studies:

- #1 Study of Semantics and Epidemiology Markers for Daily Risk Assessment of Pancreatic Cancer
- #2 Interventional Microscopic Study based on Patient-Reported Outcomes
- #3 Study of Lifestyle Choices on Elevating the Risk Factors for Pancreatic Cancer
- #4 Study of Real-time Personalized Recommendations and Metrics to Raise Awareness of Relevant Factors
- #5 Study of Improved Risk Prediction Models via Targeted Interventions that can Delay the Onset of Disease

 A "Read more" button is provided for further details.

The "Methodology" section, titled "Conceptual Approach", includes a circular diagram showing the flow from "Personalised Analytic and Predictive Models" through "HH Data Management" to "Delivery of Recommendations to Suitable Candidates". The methodology steps are:

- ✓ Extract & Analyze clinical data of Pancreatic Cancer patients
- ✓ Design personalised recommendations
- ✓ Integration of Primary & Secondary data in the HH format
- ✓ Fungal AI analytics provides real-time assessment

The screenshot shows the iHelp website homepage with the following sections:

- Consortium Partners:** A grid of logos for various partners including the European Research Center, ATC, marinaSalud, Gemelli, ENGINEERING, ICE Information Systems, INNOVATION SPRINT, Karolinska Institutet, Kodar, LEAN SCALE, SIEMENS, THE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER, and MANCHESTER.
- iHelp at a glance:** A summary section with icons and numbers: 15 Partners, 9 Partner Countries, 6 Clinical Partners, 5 Pilot Studies, and 1000000 Access to Patient.
- Latest News:** A section with three news items:
 - Tool for Enhancing the Medical Professionals Capability for Pancreatic Cancer Risk Detection** (October 26, 2021)
 - Developing Risk Prediction Models and evaluation of Interventions that can Delay / Early detect the** (October 13, 2021)
 - Toxicity risk assessment in pancreatic cancer patients – a digital trial using iHelp framework** (October 6, 2021)
- Get Started:** A section with a text input field for an email address and a 'Subscribe' button.
- Footer:** Contains the iHelp logo, 'Our Project' navigation menu, a funding notice from the European Union Horizon 2020 program, and 'Recent Posts' with links to the news items.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the iHelp website.

4.1 Search Engine Optimization

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is a continuous process that helps a website appear higher in the organic search results of Google. A SEO strategy is implemented in 2 phases: a) setup, and b) running-phase. For the setup phase, the best practices have already been applied, ensuring that the website is developed according to the latest Google recommendations. Concerning the running phase, there are several activities that will further increase the position of iHelp, e.g., Backlinks from/to high ranking and credible websites; relevant and original content with proper wording; descriptive URLs in every new page generated. These activities will also be based on Google Insights for specific keywords that the project will decide to promote in the future. The SEO performance will be checked with web tools and manual trials as well.

5 Social Media

The communication of the project through social media performs in a way to maximize the awareness and impact. Each social media channel has different audiences; therefore, the project generates and shares content through all available channels. Nowadays, a dissemination strategy cannot leave aside social media considering the heterogeneous public the latter reach at a considerable speed.

Twitter and LinkedIn are the most engaging and penetrating social media platforms. People spend the most time and constitute a great opportunity for the iHelp project to be discovered by the general and specialized public keeping them up to date on its activities. Another platform iHelp started using is YouTube, through which we communicate campaigns and videos. This social media channel is an informative and educational since a video can present and show results of the project and explain with more details on it.

5.1 Twitter

Considering that Twitter (https://twitter.com/iHelp_Project) users interact through click-link, the strategy of iHelp in Twitter is to post both project-related announcements, and related articles. In addition, this account will offer a bi-directional communication channel with people interested (mentions and direct messages). On the Twitter platform, photos are important, as they attract attention to more users reading the uploaded post (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: iHelp Twitter account.

5.2 LinkedIn

On LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovation-sprint/>) the content will aim to engage stakeholders and therefore will be more business oriented, in line with the main platform purpose (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: iHelp LinkedIn account.

5.3 YouTube

The YouTube platform is suitable for communicating video content, which based on keywords attract the audience that is interested in it. The iHelp channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSeeFSLYsDneHLMr6r62MOA>) uses this social media platform to communicate and publish video campaigns as well as keynote speeches of partners about the project (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: iHelp YouTube channel.

6 Monitoring Dissemination Activities

6.1 Dissemination Activities Tracker

The iHelp project collects information regarding dissemination activities, such as events, workshops, publications, posts, articles and press releases in 3rd portals and relevant thematic blogs/collaboration platforms to introduce iHelp and present the developments of the project (see Table 2 below).

Table 2: Dissemination Activities Tracker.

#	Type	Date	Partner	Audience	URL
1	Social Media	2021/01 – 2021/12	iSPRINT	General Public	https://twitter.com/iHelp_Project
2	Social Media	2021/01 – 2021/12	iSPRINT	General Public	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ihelp-project/
3	Press Release	2021/02/12	iSPRINT	Media	https://www.pharmiweb.com/press-release/2021-02-12/innovation-sprint-boosts-the-ai-portfolio-of-healthentia-for-clinical-research-and-ehealth-with-new-rd-projects
4	Website, Blog post	2021/03/10	iSPRINT	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/data-collection-and-advice-delivery-in-ihelp-using-healthentia/
5	Website, Blog post	2021/04/07	ICE	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/social-media-analytics-health-related-policy-making/
6	Website, Blog post	2021/04/21	ATC	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/potential-ai-in-healthcare-data/
7	Website, Blog post	2021/04/29	HDM	General Public	https://www.marinasalud.es/el-hospital-de-denia-participa-en-un-programa-europeo-de-prevencion-de-cancer-de-pancreas/
8	Website, Blog post	2021/05/12	LXS	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/database-barriers-modern-bigdata-healthcare-applications/
9	Website, Blog post	2021/05/13	UNIMAN	General Public	https://www.alliancembs.manchester.ac.uk/original-thinking-applied/original-thinkers/making-healthier-decisions/?utm_campaign=news-events&utm_medium=social&utm_source=twitter-post&utm_content=original-thinking-blog-making-healthier-decisions
10	Website, Blog post	2021/06/18	ENG	General Public	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6806237701105303553
11	Website, Blog post	2021/07/06	SIE	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/tackling-the-complexity-of-patient-oriented-strategies/
12	Website, Blog post	2021/07/12	KOD	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/ai-support-monitoring-alerting-feedback-and-evaluation-module-in-ihelp/

13	Website, Blog post	2021/07/23	UPRC	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/role-of-enhanced-semantic-interoperability-in-healthcare-domain/
14	Website, Blog post	2021/10/01	KI	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/the-role-karolinska-institutet/
16	Website, Blog post	2021/10/12	TMU	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/developing-risk-prediction-models-and-evaluation-of-interventions-that-can-delay-early-detect-the-onset-of-pancreatic-cancer/
17	Website, Blog post	2021/10/26	MUP	General Public	https://ihelp-project.eu/tool-for-enhancing-the-medical-professionals-capability-for-pancreatic-cancer-risk-detection/
18	Website, Blog post	2021/10/06	FPG	General Public	https://gemelligenerator.it/projects/ihelp/
19	Online video campaign	2021/11/19	iSPRINT	General Public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6WYHNfOEgfy

6.2 Events/Conferences Calendar

A sheet template listing the events participation of the partners has been created in order for the project consortium to be able to keep track on the project's participation to events and to report about these activities and their impact in the dissemination deliverables as well as on the project website and social media accounts (see Table 3 below).

Table 3: Events planned/attended.

#	Title	Type	Location	Date	Audience	URL
1	-	Event	Indonesia	2021/06/23	30, Scientific Community	-
2	ICTS4eHealth 2021	Conference	Online	2021/09/05	Scientific Community	https://icts4ehealth.i-car.cnr.it/
3	Talk at National Taiwan University of Science and Technology	Workshop	Taiwan	2021/10/18	30, Scientific Community	-
4	BioSMART 2021	Conference	Online	2021/12/08	Scientific Community	https://www.biosmart-conference.org/
5	Presentation of pancreatic cancer risk prediction	Conference	Manchester	2021/04/08	2000, Scientific Community	-

6.3 Publications

In order to keep the project participants' submissions and publications tracked, the respective sheet has been created. All partners are asked to fill in the information in the table each time they submit their relevant publications to scientific journals/magazines (see Table 4 below for a summary of the information tracked).

Table 4: Publication Tracker.

#	DOI	Type	Title	Journal/Magazine
1	10.1109/ISCC53001.2021.9631475	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	iHELP: Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records	2021 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)
2	Pending	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	MICSurv: Medical Image Clustering for Survival Risk Group Identification	BioSmart

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ATC	Athens Technology Center
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DSS	Decision Support System
ENG	ENGINEERING Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A
EU	European Union
FPG	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
HDM	Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud
ICE	Information Catalyst for Enterprise
iSPRINT	Innovation Sprint
KI	Karolinska Institutet
KOD	KODAR
LXS	LeanXcale
MS	Milestone
MUP	Medical University of Plovdiv
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SIE	Siemens
TG	Target Group
TMU	Taipei Medical University
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Center